

Speculation on Accelerating Charge Radiation and Quantum Bound States

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Using retarded time and Maxwell's electromagnetic equations, one may show that an accelerating charge radiates photons. This calculation, however, is based on sharply defined notions of position and time. Retarded time seems to be linked with the constraint that charge pieces at specific precise positions move with a speed c to a measurement point such that they all arrive at time t . This leads to virtual photons becoming real photons, we argued in (1), and leaving the system.

Originally when quantum mechanics was being considered to describe the motion of an electron in an atom, it was suggested that the electron should radiate because it is accelerating. This suggests, however, that one knows the position and time of an electron precisely, which is not the case in quantum mechanics. In (1), we suggested that one may describe virtual photons in the electrostatic potential ϕ and magnetic potential A through the Lorentz gauge. This led to the virtual photon being described by $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ where $E=pc$. As a result, the idea of uncertainty in motion is already associated with a virtual photon in the electric fields.

For a quantum bound state, one has constant p , i.e. constant velocity, because $W(x)=\text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and a constant v electron does not radiate. Thus, the only issue is collisions with $V(x)=\text{Sum over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx)$, and the question of whether such a collision can emit a photon.. For a bound state, even with interference, there are crests and troughs, suggesting that the idea of fixed position and time do not exist. Given these two considerations, it seems that there is no reason to necessarily expect the electron to radiate.

The correspondence principle, however, indicates that for large energy levels, a quantum bound state should become classical. As a result, there should be radiation from an electron in an atom for high energy levels, but the quantum bound state calculation does not show this. We argue that such radiation should occur when a crest/trough of the bound wavefunction fits into what is considered to be a dx . In such a case, the electron is localized in both time and space and the potential acts in a tiny dx region. There is no longer the sense of interference of $\exp(ipx)$ s because each dx is linked with its own $\exp(ip(x) x)$. With time and space being defined precisely, but the electric and magnetic fields extending outside of dx , it seems that classical electromagnetic theory, based on precise t and x , applies and radiation should occur. In other words, the electron is not in a mix of constant p states ($\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$), but is really accelerating due to localization in x and t .

Classical Electromagnetic Theory

Classical electromagnetism is based on Maxwell's equations and the Lorentz force expression. Calculations describing a moving charge (constant and accelerated motion), however, have an extra caveat. Given a fixed origin, one may measure a little piece of charge at r' vector (from the origin) as well as a measurement point r vector, also from the origin. The catch is that it is assumed that a signal, traveling at c , the speed of light in a vacuum which is constant for constant frames of references, must reach the measurement point at time t . Given that for different r' vector points the distance to the measurement point differs, the time of arrival also

differs if each charge piece sends a signal at the same time. Thus, one must introduce retarded time (2):

$$t \text{ in charge density } \longrightarrow t - R/c \text{ where } R = |\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|/c \quad ((1))$$

This key feature means that d/dr derivatives, which appear in $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ partial and $B = \text{grad } \times A$, where E, B are the electric and magnetic fields, act on the retarded time expression and not just on $1/r$ factors in the denominator. In other words, when calculating E and B , one obtains terms linked to derivatives of a dipole moment $p = q \text{ length}$ and $dp/dt = qv$ in ϕ, A . A further d/dr derivative from E and B , for the accelerating case leads to terms which drop as $1/r$ for E and B which in turn means $E \times B$ drops as $1/r^2$. When multiplied by rr (proportional to the area of a sphere) and $r \rightarrow \text{infinite}$, one obtains a finite value suggesting photons are radiated away. (For details see (2), pages 458, 459).

As a result, we argued in (1) that virtual photons carrying signals become real photons in the case of acceleration, but this depends on retarded time and the condition that one knows the exact time and position of an electron. This might seem like an obvious condition given classical mechanics for which one has $x(t)$. This is, however, not the only scenario possible even in Maxwell's classical electromagnetic equations.

In (1) we tried to argue that the dispersion relationship $E = pc$, which holds for a photon, is present in the Lorentz gauge:

$$0 = 1/c^2 d^2\phi/dt^2 + \text{grad } \text{dot } A \quad ((2))$$

We argued that one may write $\phi = \text{gamma } \sum \text{over } k \ a(k) \exp(-iEt + ikx)$ and $A_c = \text{gamma } v \phi$ for motion v_x and collected coefficients of $\exp(-iEt + ikx)$. This led to $E = kc$, for $v = c$, which is the dispersion relationship of a photon. We thus argued that virtual photons are present in ϕ and A . Here we note an extra point, namely that $\exp(-iEt + ikx)$ describes the photon. This, however, is a probabilistic type of expression linked with translational invariance because $(\exp(-iEt + ikx))^* (\exp(-iEt + ikx)) = 1$. In other words, there is probability in time and space for a photon, so one cannot pinpoint its position and time exactly. If such a situation were to apply to the electron, its time and position also could not be pinpointed and the entire notion of retarded time breaks down as does the associated radiation calculation. That does not prove that an electron without precise time and position cannot radiate, but one cannot calculate the acceleration because one cannot follow the electron using $x(t)$.

Quantum Bound State

A quantum bound state uses translational invariance and assumes that a bound particle (such as an electron) is in a constant p (hence constant v) state. Constant v states do not radiate in classical electromagnetic theory. The idea is that the electron is described by $\exp(ipx)$ which means there is uncertainty in position. The potential may be written as $V(x) = \sum \text{over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx)$ which indicates impulse hits in a translationally invariant manner. As long as these impulse hits, which change the electron from p_1 to p_2 , do not lead to radiation, then the electron is in some $\exp(ipx)$ state. The various $\exp(ipx)$ states interfere to create a result with crests and

troughs which are sizable according to the bound region (i.e. the region between classical turning points).

$$W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

Thus, an electron is always in a constant v state, except when it undergoes a rapid impulse hit which changes its p . Secondly, its position and time are not precise. Thus, it seems there is no reason for it to be radiating, at least according to the prescription given in (2) because one cannot define its acceleration in any kind of regular manner.

There exist some theories in the literature which suggest that the photon radiates, but then absorbs the emitted photon. We do not consider this case here.

Correspondence Principle

The correspondence principle suggests that for the case of a quantum energy level becoming very high (approaching infinite), the quantum bound system should become classical. A classical electron, however, radiates, whereas a quantum bound electron shows no sign of radiating. The quantum bound theory may be applied to any energy level, including very high energy levels.

We try to consider what is happening. For low energy levels, one has translation invariance and interference, i.e. different $\exp(ipx)$ s interfere and each has a wavelength comparable to the bound region. There exists a superposition of constant p (hence constant v) states. In terms of conservation of energy, however, one has the exact classical result for any energy level:

$$KE(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((4))$$

But $KE(x)$ is now a superposition average and not an exact result because one does not know the exact position or time of the electron i.e..

$$KE(x) = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W \text{ where } W = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((5))$$

Thus, there exists an exact v_{rms} , together with a position and time, but this is an average and does not correspond to a physical electron.

As energy levels increase, the crests and troughs of $W(x)$ become very narrow and begin to fit into dx , a length interval considered to be tiny in the classical world. In other words, there is localization in position and so there should also be localization in the delivery of an impulse hit and time as well. There is no longer superposition of constant $p \exp(ipx)$ s because an $\exp(ip(x) x)$'s wavelength (or several wavelengths) fit into each dx . In such a case, the electron position and time are known and it actually accelerates in a deterministic manner. In such a case, one may use retarded time in Maxwell's electromagnetic equations and obtain radiation results.

Thus, we suggest that radiation emission starts to appear with the localization of the electron in time and space, which should occur for large energy levels. It is not clear at which energy level one should start to see emission.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that the theory of radiation of an accelerating electron requires the notion of retarded time and also of precise position and time values for the electron. In a quantum bound state, such precision does not exist. There is no notion of exact acceleration because one has a probability $\exp(ipx)$ to be in a constant p (v) state which does not radiate. Given that many different p values may exist, one has an OR situation or interference $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. This leads to a crest/trough pattern with crests and troughs having different heights and widths, but the widths are comparable to the bound region. As long as the impulse hits by $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ don't create radiation, there is no reason to assume radiation because there is no acceleration.

As the energy level increases, the electron becomes localized in space and time, i.e. a crest-trough wavelength fits into a length dx considered to be tiny. The uncertainty in position is now dx which is negligible classically. Thus, one knows the electron position at time t and there is the sense of acceleration. There is no long superposition of $\exp(ipx)$ s over a large length. In such a situation, retarded time makes sense and one may use the classical calculation which suggests radiation from an accelerating charge. It is not clear at what energy level this localization is considered to be sharp enough to produce radiated photons.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Retarded Time and Radiation from an Accelerated Charge (preprint, zenodo, 2024)
2. Reitz, J. and Milford, F. and Christy, R. Foundations of Electromagnetic Theory (Addison Wesley 1980)